

An Efficient Classification of Online News using Machine Learning

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Abstract: Now-a-days, businesses are being forced to adopt new strategies and resources in order to provide improved navigation, processing, and management of high-dimensional data due to the tremendous increase in web-based online content. Ninety percent of data on the Internet is unstructured. There are a number of ways to convert this unstructured data into organized, usable data, and one such method is categorization. Sorting knowledge into a useful set of categories is important and required. Automatic text categorization is desperately needed to categorize the growing number of machine-readable documents. Text labelling is a supervised learning approach that groups unlabelled texts into predetermined classes of labelled documents. This study presents a framework for the automated classification of internet news items and reviews some of the current methods for doing so. It was attempted using a variety of classifiers to get high accuracy. Using a Bayesian classifier, our experimental approach produced results with 93% accuracy and presented confusion measures.

Keywords: *text classification; naïve Bayes; support vector machine; news articles*

Introduction: The enormous amount of digital material available now is only going to get bigger. One of the main ways to organize and manage this massive volume of data is to automatically classify texts into pre-existing groups. This type of textual data is produced by several sources and may be found in publications, journals, web pages, emails, conference materials, editorials, digital/electronic papers, and publications. Many individuals no longer rely solely on printed materials like books, periodicals, and newspapers for their daily information needs; instead, they use various internet sources. Access to this kind of information has been easier, but managing it is still hard because of the complexity of knowledge structure. One of the most important ways to properly categorize this type of digital material is to organize it.

Text retrieval, information abstraction and summarization, and question answering all heavily rely on text categorization. Typically, the online data utilized for categorization comes from a variety of sources, including newsgroups, bulletin boards, printed or broadcast media, movie reviews, and adverts. Automatic text classification is crucial due to their heterogeneous nature, which includes several sources, distinct vocabularies, formats, and writing styles for texts [1]. Owing to the massive volume of text that is kept in electronic format, it is required to comprehend, analyze, and extract comparable features from this data that may be helpful in decision-making [2, 3, 4].

Text classification is the process of classifying a document under an existing category (Fig. 1). Depending on the classifications, a document may have one or more labels. When a document is assigned to a single class, it is referred to as a single label; if it is assigned to many classes, it is referred to as a multi-label document [5].

Fig. 1: Text classification process

Feature selection, document representation, algorithm application, and performance evaluation are all included in text categorization. Due to the rapid expansion of online commerce and the massive availability of text documents, categorization is a necessary method for extracting important information from documents. Currently, text information management and organization are regarded as essential practices [6]. k-Nearest Neighbour [9], neural networks [8], support vector machines [7], and naïve Bayesian [10] classification are some examples of techniques that may be utilized to build classification schemes.

Online news stories are one place where we come with a significant volume of content on a regular basis. People want to read just news items related to their interests since they are concerned about their busy lifestyles as a result of advancements in information technology [11]. Finding relevant news on a person's interests can be a difficult undertaking because many news pieces are informative but may not be very important. A person's attraction may depend on a variety of elements, including the news source and the nature of the stories [12]. Here, we categorize the news stories according to their genre or category. Consider a person who likes to read political news, for instance. Given that news pieces abound on the internet, it would be difficult for a certain person to read solely political publications.

In this study, we have used machine-learning algorithms to tailor the news items for a certain category. Politics, criminal activity, sports, entertainment, or global news might be the category. Using the approximately 75,000 news stories in the Huff Post data set, we trained and evaluated the categorization model. Following training and testing, we used this model to analyze news stories from many real-time news websites, including the Quint, the Hindu, the Print, and Indian Express.

Related Work: As handling large text datasets becomes more and more necessary, text categorization is becoming a prominent and active area of data mining study. The exponential rise of digital textual information makes it imperative to manage textual data properly in order to swiftly search for and retrieve any document [14, 15].

Text categorization assigns classifications from a category of predefined classes to unlabelled text documents using special criteria. Text categorization is usually done manually, which is an expensive and very time-consuming because the classification rules are created by hand, solely. As a result, machine learning is an additional approach that classifies texts by automatically creating rules [16] itself.

Many classifiers are available, including association-based classification [17, 18, 19], term graph models [20, 21], decision trees (DT) [22, 23], neural networks [8, 9, 10], Bayesian classification [10], Nearest Neighbour (KNN) [9], and support vector machines [7, 8, 9]. The machine learning

techniques described are widely used by writers; a quick analysis of these approaches led to the creation of the table below.

Year	Datasets	Algorithm	Salient Features
2014	Reuter-21578	KNN	In comparison to Naïve Bayes and Term Graph, KNN has the highest accuracy. The main downside is that it has the highest temporal complexity when compared to other options.
2014	Sohu laboratory corpus	SVM-KNN	The SVM-KNN method will increase the classifier's effectiveness by providing suggestions and enhancing the classifying probability. This approach raises the minimal processing complexity. SVM is also quick and effective for classification.
2015	Single-label news corpus	SVM, TF-IDF	The authors employed issue transformation and algorithm adoption techniques for the categorization of news articles from Indonesia. With an f-measure of 85.13%, the authors' combination strategy for automatically identifying news stories yields higher results.
2015	Reuters- 21578	Hyper Rectangular Keyword Extraction	Based on the document categorization hyperrectangle approach, the authors suggested crucial extraction. Comparing this method to other classification techniques, the results are outstanding and accurate.
2015	Czech News Articles	Linear SVC, SGD, PA, NB	The authors suggested a technique to improve multi-document classification's classification accuracy. Compared to other classifiers, the Naïve Bayes baseline classifier outperformed them.
2016	Various news websites	Naïve Bayes (NB)	Structure features and URL content were used to categorize different news webpages. When applied to the same dataset, the naïve Bayes algorithm produced superior results than the then current methods.
2016	News articles of emotional topics	NB, C45, DT, SVM vectors, Winnow, Balanced Winnow, and Max Entropy	To analyze the emotion of news items, the writers tried their hand at hierarchical categorization. Better results were obtained when SVM and TF-IDF were applied with six and four classification methods, respectively.
2016	Stock new of China	Softmax training algorithm, Weighted sort algorithm, and selection algorithm	For making investment decisions, authors classified stock news by proposing a novel algorithm. The authors achieved better accuracy and availability with this method compared with a general algorithm.
2016	Online news articles	Neural Network Classifier	To analyze the emotion of news items, the writers tried their hand at hierarchical categorization. Better results were obtained when SVM and TF-IDF were applied with six and four classification methods, respectively.

2017	Various news websites articles	Naïve Bayes, SVM, Random Forest	When compared to Random Forest and Naïve Bayes, the SVM performed the worst. SVM also required a lot of training time.
2017	Korean News Articles	KNN, NB, SVM, and Logistic Regression (LR)	The author used four classifiers in two investigations that were conducted. Study 1 attained a better degree of accuracy since its data were simpler. The categorization findings could have been impacted by Study 2, whose data had higher levels of complexity.
2017	Reuters.com news articles and Gold Standard dataset	SVM, SDG, LR	The authors categorized text articles using a variety of classification techniques in order to identify opinion, spam, and false news. Adding more features helped classifiers produce better results.
2017	Yahoo News US Edition	Keyword matching, Newsmap	A semi-supervised classifier for the categorization of geographic news was created by the project. Comparing the total classification accuracy to other conventional classifiers, it was comparatively low at 0.80.
2018	NLPCC2014, REV1-v2	Attention GRU Bi-RNN	The authors suggested a bi-directional recurrent neural network method that performed classification on two datasets and achieved a high accuracy of 83.9 compared to previous classifiers. The algorithm was centered around the process of neural network interest.
2018	BR news dataset US news dataset	ANOVA, SVM	The authors suggested a bi-directional recurrent neural network method that performed classification on two datasets and achieved a high accuracy of 83.9 compared to previous classifiers. The algorithm was centered around the process of neural network interest.
2018	Indonesian news articles	Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA)	The authors suggested a bi-directional recurrent neural network method that performed classification on two datasets and achieved a high accuracy of 83.9 compared to previous classifiers. The algorithm was centered around the process of neural network interest.
2018	China News	SVM, CNN, MAXENT	For the purpose of classifying Chinese news stories, the authors used three algorithms in two schemes. SVM outperformed the other two.
2019	News articles and tweets	Word2vec Convolutional Neural Networks	Twitter and news articles are categorized into similar and unrelated terms using an algorithm. By understanding the semantic relationships between words, Word2vec improved performance.
2019	Arabic news articles from websites	SVM, NB, DT, RF, LR	The project categorized news articles in Arabic that were gathered from several news websites. SVM outperformed all other classifiers, with an 87% accuracy rate.

2019	Indonesian news articles	Convolutional neural networks, recurrent neural networks	In order to get real-time financial risk information, the team carried out a methodical classification of risk documents. The authors used a large amount of data to get better categorization results. But annotating fresh data by hand was a laborious procedure.
2019	Thai PBS, Khaosod, and Dailynews	SVM, Decision Tree, Deep Learning	Using Thai news as a dataset, the authors spoke about how well different classifiers performed. SVM and Decision Tree fared worse than Deep Learning.
2019	BBC datasets, five groups of 20Newsgroup	SVM, Naïve Bayes, Bi-LSTM, LSTM, CNN	Two datasets of Chinese news were classified using five classifiers in this work. Additionally, they outlined the distinction between ML and DL classification, pointing out that ML required preprocessing and feature extraction and was a more laborious classification method. On the other hand, DL didn't need any cleaning tasks. But they got the highest precision and efficient, dependable outcomes using ML.
2020	Society channel of Sina	C4.5 Decision Tree Algorithm	The writers suggested categorizing the feelings expressed in news stories. They divided feelings into categories: fear, joy, and melancholy. This approach was compared to the SVM classifier and yielded a high accuracy of 87.83%.
2020	Uzbek Daryo online news	SVM, DT, RF, LR, Multinomial Naive Bayes	For the Uzbek language news article categorization, the authors employed six different algorithms. At 86.88%, the method's accuracy was the greatest.
2020	Tigrigna news dataset	SVM, DT, LR, RF, KNN, etc.	After building the Tigrigna news dataset, the authors experimented with eight different classifiers. SVM fared better than other categorization schemes. It also obtained the best accuracy.

Table 1: Correlated Text categorization efforts by different authors

A selection of the recent publications that we studied are shown in Table 1. Numerous academics examined and classified writings written in a number of languages, including Chinese [39] and Korean [33]. Arabic language classification was still covered by a number of works [41], providing insight into scholarly works based on the use of traditional supervised machine learning classifiers such as SVM [34, 37], KNN [24, 25], Decision Tree [45], and Naïve Bayes [7, 29]. The overall output was greater even though other writers concentrated on deep learning [42] and neural networks [32] for categorization. Lastly, it is clear that the consistency of the data source severely hampered the performance of the classification algorithm in all languages, as the superfluous and repeated features of the data weakened the accuracy and output of the classifier.

Experimental Design:

Based on the above literature, we proposed a framework to perform text classification of English news articles obtained from various Indian news websites. For ease of understanding, we divide the proposed framework into three main modules: Data Extraction, Data Preprocessing, and Classifier Module as illustrated in Fig. 2.

Data preparation is the first step to clean up the dataset. The dataset is then split into train and test halves. Of the dataset, train data comprise 70% and test data 30%. In the next module, the classifier is trained to predict the class labels for the gathered news items and to assign a category label in the

subsequent stage. Consequently, some sort of performance indicator is used to evaluate the classifier's performance. Each module is explained in depth in the next section.

Fig. 2: News article classification process.

Data Extraction: As seen in Fig. 2, the procedure begins with a data gathering module that crawls news items from seven distinct news websites. First, tweepy is used to crawl Twitter for tweets from different news Twitter accounts. Tweet URLs that were crawled yielded a variety of news items. Additionally, by accessing each URL, the news article web pages are collected from each news website. Seven news websites are used by the data extraction module to download news items and tweets.

Additionally, we used a dataset from Huff Post that includes around 75,000 news headlines from 2012 to 2018 together with information about their content and categorization. Eight categories comprise these news articles: business, politics, entertainment, crime, sports, media, and technology. Fig. 3 displays the proportion of each genre of news stories.

Fig. 3: Percentage of each news article category.

Data Pre-processing: The dataset is cleaned using the data preparation module, which is regarded as a crucial step in obtaining quality outcomes. To begin with, we tokenize articles using a module that converts character groups into strings with discernible meaning. Next, since stop words like "what" and "the" are often used and have little prominence, we eliminate them using the Python nltk module.

Label Encoding: The Scikit-Learn library's LabelEncoder class was utilized to convert numerical data that might be understood by a model from categorical text input. Using the LabelEncoder class from the Scikit-learn package, we encode the first column before fitting and transforming its data. The old text data was then replaced with the newly encoded data.

Train-Test Split: One named classification of the news articles gathered from seven distinct news websites is part of our effort. We split our dataset into 70% for training and 30% for testing in order to facilitate training and testing. There were 52635 labelled news items in the training data set and 22558 news articles in the testing set. We fitted the final model to the training data using the 10-fold cross-validation technique, and then we assessed it using the unclassified data to provide evaluation metrics with the least amount of bias.

Training the Model: The classifier's input data consists of the training set and the set of labels that go with it. The labels "Crime," "Entertainment," "World News," "Politics," "Sports," "Business," "Media," and "Tech" are the ones we utilized in conjunction with the training set. Processed news pieces were assigned numbers based on the predetermined category tag. News items and the labels have to be vectorized as the classifier input is made up of two vectors. After these two things were vectorized, they served as an input to the classifier.

Testing the Model: After the classifier was trained using the training data, the classifier model was evaluated using the testing data. The category of the associated news articles was predicted by the classifier. With 93% accuracy, the Naive Bayes classifier outperformed the others. Additionally, our methodology guarantees that the aforementioned "business" item would fall under the same heading.

Performance Metrics: For the implementation of all the classification algorithms, we used Scikit-learn. In order to illustrate the Act imbalances on traditional measuring tools like accuracy, recall, and precision, the performance metrics for classifiers were examined. These metrics make use of information from categorization jobs concerning the anticipated and actual classes. All potential outcomes of the research might be reflected in the confusion matrix that follows.

		PREDICTED	
		Positive	Negative
ACTUAL	Positive	True Positive (TP)	False Negative (FN)
	Negative	False Positive (FP)	True Negative (TN)

Table 2: Confusion Matrix

Positive cases are those in which an instance is classified as belonging to a class; negative cases are those in which an instance is not classified as belonging to any particular class. When an occurrence is correctly identified as belonging to the positive category, it is referred to as a true positive (TP). These cases, which belong to the positive cases but are mistakenly labeled as negative, are known as false negatives (FN). These cases, which belong to the negative category but are mistakenly labeled as positive, are known as false positives (FP). It is accurate to classify the events as belonging to the negative situation. We refer to this as true negatives (TN). A few of the performance measures derived from the confusion matrix are highlighted below.

Accuracy: The classifier's accuracy may be calculated by dividing its total number of correct predictions by the total amount of data collected [48]. The precision stated mathematically as:

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + FP + TN + FN}$$

The sum of all inaccurate projections divided by the total number of datasets is the error rate, or ERR. 0.0 represents the minimum error rate, while 1.0 represents the maximum. The mistake stated mathematically as

$$Error\ Rate = 1 - Accuracy$$

Precision: The number of articles that the classifier estimates belong to a certain category (True Positive and False Positive) divided by the number of articles that are correctly recognized (True Positive). The mathematical version of precision [48] is:

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}$$

Recall: A recall is the proportion of accurately predicted positive articles to all articles in the actual class [49]. In mathematical terms, the recall is represented as:

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$$

The majority of positive cases (TP + FN) are assumed to be assessed as positive (TP) in the case of a good recall. More FP measurements and decreased average accuracy are probably in store in this scenario. A low recall suggests that there is a substantial FN volume, which is classified as negative even though it should have been positive. This guarantees that, should a favourable situation be discovered, we will be more certain in it.

Accuracy is not achieved on unbalanced classification when researchers employ machine learning approaches. Higher accuracy may be achieved in unbalanced settings since all the data is expected to belong to the majority class. As a result, the machine learning community accepts the F1 score and the receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve as reasonable metrics. The ROC curve illustrates the trade-off between false positive and genuine positive. It would likely only represent precision for the real positives when the false positives are ignored and the focus is skewed. The scores would, however, unquestionably reflect the recall if the true positives are disregarded and the focus is skewed toward the false positives. The area under the curve (AUC) represents the effectiveness of the classifier.

F1-Score: The F1 score is calculated as the harmonic mean of recall and accuracy. The F1 score [50] is created by summing Precision and Recall. For the F1 score, 1 and 0 are the best and lowest values, respectively. Because it includes both precision and recall, it is more effective to employ a single number for measurement as opposed to two. Mathematically it is expressed as:

$$F1 = \frac{2 * Precision * Recall}{Precision + Recall}$$

Results and Analysis: Table 3 shows the evaluation of comparative results of SVM, LR, KNN, and Naive Bayes algorithms employing different news websites in terms of all indicated performance criteria for each classification technique tested on our dataset. The F1 score and accuracy are quite comparable. The graphical examination of all four methods is shown in Figure 6.

Fig. 4: Performance comparison of all the classifiers

With an accuracy of 93.0%, the Naive Bayes classifier outperformed the other three. Furthermore, the KNN classifier had the lowest score at 72.0%. Figures 5 and 6 display the confusion matrices for the best NB and poorest KNN classifiers.

Classifier output by unbalanced ratios is seen in Figure 9. Naive Bayes outperformed the other classifiers when training data for minority groups was sparser than for other methods. It attained a 0.5 F1 score with an 11% imbalance, whereas other scores with a comparable F1 score reached 22% of the imbalance. Although certain algorithms finally showed improved results as additional class imbalance training data were provided, the classifier's efficiency did not improve when the unbalanced levels dropped to 44%. Overall, the KNN classifier produced the lowest result. While most classifiers produced an average F1 score over 0.7 at a disparity rate of 44 percent, it required an imbalance level of 66 percent to acquire an average F1 score above 0.7. The most unbalanced settings were best suited for Naive Bayes.

Fig. 5: Confusion matrix for Naive Bayes classifier

Fig. 7: Confusion matrix for the KNN classifier.

Fig. 9: Performance of classifiers

Conclusion: In this study, we developed a single-class text classification system for online news items. An example dataset of over 75,000 news articles categorized with their tags and sourced from seven different sources was showcased. The phases of dataset generation, cleansing, and collecting were established. In order to assess our dataset, we included four different classifiers. We classified the dataset using Naïve Bayes and a few other classification algorithms. We compared the results of the different classifiers from seven different sites. The results show that Naïve Bayes performed better than most classifiers and provides adequate classification accuracy when working with different news datasets. There are several ways to expand this study. Our long-term goal is to identify and use a categorization system across multiple regional languages.

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